

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 4, No. 11; November 28, 1998

Dear Readers:

This is the last but one number of volume 4 of J.UCS. Is it not incredible that J.UCS is soon in its fifth year?

I am sure you will like the contributions in this issue. So that you and others also can enjoy future issues, please continue to help by sending or soliciting high quality contributions!

There is one major item I have to report on this time: it was planned that as of '99, J.UCS will go commercial (US \$200.- for the 6 years, i.e. 72 issues, which is less than \$3.- per issue). A final decision on how to go about this, and how to mirror J.UCS world-wide was to be taken this December. However, a few weeks ago the publishing giant Bertelsmann purchased Springer, and so new discussions will have to take place with possibly a new team early next year. I guess the good news is: J.UCS will thus remain free of charge for the time being.

Well, this is a nice X-mas present. And, yes, it is time for me to wish you all the best for the X-mas season: this is the last issue to appear before X-mas, issue 12 will appear as usual at the end of December, so I guess I can still save my best wishes for 1999 for the next issue!

Enough for now, hope you are not too much under stress due to the upcoming X-mas celebrations so that you can still find time to do some quiet reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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